

REGULAR ARTICLE

Flood Modeling using Hydrologic Engineering Center's - Hydrologic Modeling System (HEC-HMS) and River Analysis System (HEC-RAS) for a Micro Watershed in Castilla, Sorsogon

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Abstract: The study generated a model to analyze the watershed response of Mayon micro watershed in Castilla, Sorsogon, Philippines to storm events and to identify areas of inundation for possible future interventions. Remotely-sensed and physically evaluated data were processed using ArcMap, HEC Geo HMS, ArcHydro, HEC HMS, HEC Geo RAS and HEC RAS. One (1) storm event (*TS Ambo*) was used for calibration, and three (3) other storm events (*TS Ofel*, *TD Marce*, and *TS Tisoy*) were used for validation. Nash Sutcliffe Efficiency, Percentage Error in Peak, Percentage Error in volume, and Root Mean Square error (RMSE) were used to evaluate model performance in which, for *TS Ofel* is equal to 0.728, 10.00%, 17.41% and 0.3 cu m/sec respectively, indicating a satisfactory model performance for the identified micro watershed. For *TD Marce*, model performance was -0.31, 22.22%, 17.73% and 0.3 cu m/sec. Graphical and visual analysis of modelled and actual flow depth for *TS Tisoy* are near identical. Results revealed that the calibrated model performed satisfactorily in predicting the response of the micro watershed in identical storm events (Tropical storm category) as in calibration and less satisfactory on short duration, low

intensity storm events such as TD Marce. Also, a 7.23 hr – 2 year storm will submerge critical road crossings (Purok 6 road crossing - Station 136.815) and Cubao area - Station 0), and will cause inundation of agricultural areas in the lower reaches. These areas need interventions for flood mitigation and prevention.

Keywords: Hydrology and Environment; Hydrologic and hydraulic modeling; watershed modeling; Applied research; Sorsogon, Philippines

1. Introduction

Flooding and excessive runoff causes damaging impact to the country. Major floods on record include typhoon Milenyo in 2007 which devastated the Provinces of Albay and Sorsogon, and Ondoy in 2009, adversely affecting major parts of the National Capital Region. On a data compiled by the National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (NDRRMC), the country experiences about 10 water-related disaster events annually. This causes an economic damage that is equivalent to 0.1 percent (US\$0.225B in 2011, approximately equal to Php 9.738B at 43.28 pesos to 1 US dollar exchange rate) of the country's current Gross Domestic Product (GDP) earnings. In 2017 alone, the economic cost of 22 tropical cyclones, flash floods, and inter-tropical convergence zones amounted to Php 6.446 billion [1].

The devastating effects of these calamities had always prompted the use of innovative measures for prevention. Most countries are seeking ways to forecast these events to conduct pre-emptive activities and measures. But forecasting of hydrologic events requires the assessment of hydrologic and hydraulic response of a watershed. Modeling that will integrate watershed characteristics to hydrologic processes is an ideal tool to predict the response of a watershed. However, this needs to be calibrated carefully using site-specific parameters to produce reliable results, and a thorough study is needed particularly for areas with which is prone to flooding but with limited data.

Barangay Mayon, the subject of the study is located at Castilla in the province of Sorsogon

Figure A 1). With the barangay's terrain and proximity to water conveyance channels, the locals experiences flooding almost annually. Torrential rains which occurred last October 2017, December 2017, and January of 2018 caused flooding of the area. And although it is considered as an important hub for agricultural development of the province, very limited data was available for modeling of its watershed.

With these, a study on flood modeling using the United States Army Corps of Engineers' Hydrologic Engineering Center-Hydrologic Modeling System (HEC-HMS) and Hydrologic Engineering Center-River Analysis System (HEC-RAS) was conducted on a micro watershed draining to Mayon, Castilla, Sorsogon. It involved sensitivity analysis, calibration, and validation of the model, including evaluation of the model's predicting ability.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 *Hydrologic Modeling using HEC HMS*

The HEC-HMS is designed to simulate the precipitation - runoff processes of dendritic watershed systems [2]. It utilizes algorithms for modeling baseflow, transformation, and loss as shown in Figure 1. The study used a Recession model for simulating baseflow. Data required for input are initial discharge, ratio to peak, and recession constant. For the transform method, the SCS unit hydrograph procedures was used due to terrain characteristics [3]. The Peak Rate Factor was determined based on watershed characteristics. Lag time was evaluated using the modified Snyder procedure [4].

The loss model needs determination of the Initial abstraction ratio, Curve Number, and the percentage of impervious areas [5]. Muskingum-Cunge 8-point cross section configuration routing method was used for modeling channel flow. This was considered due to the slope of the area [6]. Input parameters such as reach lengths, Manning's roughness coefficients (n), and channel cross section

shapes were extracted from a Digital Elevation Model (DEM) (Figure A 2) and refined through actual measurement and inspection of the channel. Land cover and other parameters were evaluated using a combination of satellite images processed in ArcMap, and ocular inspection [7].

Figure 1. Schematic for hydrologic modeling using HEC-HMS

2.1.1. Calibration

Calibration involved the comparison of initial simulation outputs to an observed storm event. This required the optimization of initial input parameters to fit with the flow hydrograph of a storm event.

- Estimation of Initial Input Parameters for the Models

The input parameters for the baseflow method were estimated based on current conditions. Initial discharge, ratio-to-peak, and the recession constant were determined based on actual observations. For the SCS unit Hydrograph procedures, Peak Runoff factor (Table 1) was estimated by evaluating the terrain based on ocular inspection and analysis of a DEM for the area in a GIS platform [8].

Table 1. Peak Runoff Factor Settings for the sub-basins.

Sub watersheds	Description	PRF
820	Mountainous	550
830	Rolling, Hilly	500
930	Riceland, mixed	250
940	Riceland	150

The SCS Curve Number (CN) method was used for the Loss Model. This was selected due to its applicability to the watershed [9]. It involve the computation of a CN based on Land use, land cover (

Figure A 3), soil properties, area, and the Antecedent Runoff Condition (ARC) (Table 2). It was done by digitizing satellite images from Google Earth, and was verified through site inspection. A combination of HEC GeoHMS and ArcHydro utilities was used in the preparation of a Curve Number grid.

Table 2. Sub basins' CN (ARC 1), Maximum Potential Retention (S) and Initial Abstraction (Ia) values

. Code	Sub Basin Name	Area (ha)	Basin CN	Max. Potential Retention (S), cm	Initial Abstraction (Ia) cm
W820	Maypangi	464.68	52.74	340.29	68.06
W830	SSC	64.09	55.92	200.21	40.04
W930	Mayon	24.6	56.35	196.79	39.36
W940	Cubao	46.42	57.94	184.40	36.88

- Preparation of Meteorological data The boundaries of the study area were delineated. As shown in Table 2, it was divided into four (4) sub basins: W820–Maypangi; W830-SSC; W930-Camacho; and W940-Cubao. A DEM was processed to identify stream networks including the main watershed outlet.

The rain gaging station is located at W930 and the watershed outlet is at W940. An automatic recording rain gage was installed to measure hourly rates of rainfall during the storm event (Table A 2). Also, flow rates were measured at the same time in the watershed outlet for the construction of a flow hydrograph. Four (4) storm events was used for the study. One for calibration (Tropical Storm Ambo last May 14-15, 2020); and three (3) for validation of the optimized model (TS Ofel, October 14-15, 2020) Tropical Depression Marce (September 22-23, 2020), and TS Tisoy December 1-2, 2019).

- Sensitivity Analysis and Calibration

Sensitivity analysis was done to determine the parameters that should be precisely estimated. It indicated the level on which a parameter adjustment could affect model output. This was done by varying model inputs in equal percentage and analysing the sensitivity levels.

Calibration involved the optimization of initial input parameters to “fit” with the model output with the observed flow hydrograph at the watershed outlet (Cubao, Mayon, Castilla, Sorsogon). Manual and automated calibration was conducted to match the peak flow rates and the time of peak flow [10].

- Validation

The criteria used in the evaluation of the optimized model against observed values were the following: Nash Sutcliffe Efficiency, Root Mean Square Error, Percentage Error in Peak, Percentage Error in volume, time difference for peaking, and Residual volume. Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE) is a normalized statistic that determines the relative magnitude of the residual variance compared to the measure data variance [11]. The Percentage error in volume and the percentage error in peak flow were computed by determining the difference between the observed and modelled values, and dividing it by the observe value, then multiplying the results by 100 to have the results in percent.

“NSE ranges between $-\infty$ and 1.0 (1 inclusive), with NSE = 1 being the optimal value. Results between 0.0 and 1.0 are generally viewed as acceptable levels of performance” [12]. The difference between time of peaks and, also the residual volume were analyzed. This is the difference between observed and computed values, which is either negative or positive for the residual amount.

2.2. Hydraulic Modeling using HEC-RAS

Hydraulic model development in HEC-RAS was done by following five main steps (USACE, HEC RAS River Analysis System User's Manual, 2016) [13]: (1) starting a new project; (2) Entering geometric data; (3) Entering flow data and boundary conditions; (4) Performing the hydraulic calculations; and (5)

Viewing and printing results. But, prior to these, pre-processing of data was done using HEC GeoRAS in a GIS program.

A DEM was analyzed to produce a river hydraulic model. Bank lines and stream center lines were digitized with a combination of Google Earth image and GIS utilities. Stream bank properties were evaluated to estimate Manning's roughness coefficients for each reach and station. Following procedures on stream characterization, both streambanks were evaluated (Table 3, Table 4 and (Table A 1). About 70 bank stations were characterized in the downstream side, 94 from the upstream side, and 44 from the tributary. Average distance per cross section are 22.28 m, 29.81 m, and 16.90 m respectively. The distance between cross sections was reduced to provide more details on the channel characteristics which has high meandering ratio as compared to the straight path in between meanders.

Table 3. Manning's n estimates for Mayon Creek: Right of Bank - looking downstream.

Reach	Location	Character of Channel	Relative Effect of Obstruction	Vegetation and Flow Conditions	Composite N
390	Purok 6	0.020	0.030	0.040	0.090
420	TESDA	0.020	0.035	0.050	0.105
430	Camacho	0.020	0.035	0.050	0.105
450	PNR Tracks	0.020	0.025	0.030	0.075
470	Cubao 1	0.020	0.020	0.025	0.065
480	Cubao 2	0.020	0.025	0.030	0.075
500	Cubao 3	0.025	0.010	0.010	0.045

Table 4. Manning's n estimates for Mayon Creek: Left of Bank - looking downstream

Reach	Location	Character of channel	Relative effect of obstruction	Vegetation and flow conditions	Composite n
390	Purok 6	0.02	0.020	0.040	0.080
420	TESDA	0.02	0.030	0.050	0.100
430	Camacho	0.02	0.030	0.050	0.100
450	PNR Tracks	0.02	0.025	0.030	0.075
470	Cubao 1	0.02	0.020	0.025	0.065
480	Cubao 2	0.02	0.025	0.030	0.075
500	Cubao 3	0.02	0.015	0.005	0.040

The computed and estimated watershed parameters were compiled and inputted on the various models within HEC-RAS. Simulations were conducted and compared with actual measurements to evaluate the predicting ability of the model.

3. Results

3.1 Hydrologic modeling using HEC-HMS

3.1.1 Initial simulation

Initial input parameters were used to model the watershed response using tropical Storm Ambo data. The peak flow and the time of peak was considered in the study as it was identified also in similar studies [14] as an important aspect in flood modeling and disaster mitigation. The results of the initial

simulation as shown in Figure 2 resulted to an NSE of 0.051 [12], except for the more stringent measure using the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) with a value of 1.5 cu.m/sec which is less than satisfactory. The computed runoff has a volume of 139.34 mm is compared to the observed volume of 87.07 mm resulting to a volume residual of 52 mm.

Graphical analysis shows that the time of peak flow is the same for both observed and modelled events. It occurred six (6) hours after the peak rainfall. This indicates a good relationship between the model and the observed hydrograph.

Figure 2. Hydrographs of initial simulation and observed events during TS Ambo (May 14-15, 2020) at Cubao outlet, Mayon, Castilla, Sorsogon

3.1.2 Sensitivity analysis

Sensitivity analysis of the objective functions for the loss model yield the highest value for CN at 1.49. This indicates that changes in the value will have the highest impact on the model output. This was also reported in previous studies [15] which was conducted on the sensitivity of the curve number. It could also be noted that transform model is sensitive to changes in Lag time.

3.1.3 Calibration

The resulting model has an NSE of 0.973 and an RMSE of 0.3 m/sec. These values indicate an acceptable level of performance for simulating events with reference to the observed event. It is considered as a better predictor compared to the mean of the observed values. Although the optimized model slightly underestimated the peak discharge by 1.13 cu. m/sec and, the volume by 1.37 mm. analysis of Figure 4 shows that the peak runoff, and time of peak is similar at it occurred six (6) hours after the peak of rainfall, Also, the RMSE value approaches zero value (0.3 m/sec) as compared to the initial simulation, indicated a better performance.

Analysis on the subbasins showed flow levels at the uppermost sub basin (W820) outlet (Road crossing, Purok 6) at 5.7 cu m/sec and it occurred at 8:30 AM of 15May2020. This is equivalent to 82.61% of the total flow that had occurred in the watershed outlet. NSE value at the sub basin outlet is at 0.821 which is satisfactory. Peak flow at the watershed outlet occurred at 10:00 AM.

Figure 3. Hydrographs of calibrated model and the observed events (TS Ambo, May 14-15, 2020)

The model results are shown in Table 5. The time of peak is almost similar to all simulations, Relative errors due to differences between observed and modeled values are indicated. It reveals that the calibrated model has an NSE of 0.928 which indicate a very good correlation between adjusted optimized parameters and observed event. There is a slight time difference on the time of peak, but careful analysis could show that the peak flow from 9:00 to 10:00 has a very slight difference.

Table 5. Computed and modelled (before and after calibration) runoff volumes, and error functions for (a) modelled before calibration, and (b) after calibration using TS Ambo data

Statistical Measure	Before calibration		After calibration	
	Modelled	Observed	Modelled	Observed
Volume of Runoff (mm)	119.34	87.1	91.93	87.1
Peak Discharge (cu m/sec)	11.2	6.9	6.7	6.9
Date and Time of Peak Discharge	10:00 AM, May 15, 2020	10:00 AM, May 15, 2020	9:00 AM, May 15, 2020	10:00 AM, May 15, 2020
Root Mean Square Error (cu m/sec)	1.5		0.4	
Percentage Error in volume	37		5.54	
Nash Sutcliffe Efficiency	0.051		0.928	
Residual	32.24 mm		4.83 mm	

3.1.4 Validation

Adjustment on the calibrated model was done due to the effects of previous rainfall occurrences. Curve number values were adjusted to ARC III from ARC I. Validation was conducted on three (3) storm events. TS Ofel has almost the same characteristics with the event used in calibration. TD Marce has a shorter duration and a very low intensity, and for TS Tisoy, although it occurred with almost the same intensity with TS Ambo, rainfall and flow data was not available, so rainfall averaging was done using data from two PAGASA stations (Juban, Sorsogon and Legaspi City, Philippines).

For tropical storm Ofel (October 14-15, 2020), rainfall data collected amounted to 76.40 mm with an average intensity of 3.32 mm/hr. Peak flow of 3.30 cu m/sec was computed to occur on 20:00 October 14, 2020. Of the total rainfall depth of 76.4 mm, about 13.75% (10.51 mm) was lost to infiltration.

Figure 4a shows that the time of peak occurrence is the same at 20:00 October 14, 2020, except for the sub-peaks that had occurred 1 to 4 hours earlier than actual measurements.

Tropical depression Marce which occurred September 22 to 23, 2020 had an advance type of rainfall pattern and continued at a very low intensity for 6 hours at an average intensity of 0.2 mm per hours. Total storm depth was recorded at 31.90 mm. Modeled and observed hydrographs are nearly similar in shape, but the time of peak flow occurrence is not the same (

Figure 4b). This is considered a limitation for the model [6]. The storm to be modelled should have almost similar characteristics with that used in calibration.

Figure 4. Flow computation for modelled and observed flow data at Mayon Micro watershed outlet, Mayon, castilla, Sorsogon using (a) TS Ofel data (October 14-15, 2020); (b) TD marce, September 22 to 23, 2020.

3.1.5 Summary of Model Performance

Goodness of fit indicators (Table 6) suggests that the model could be a reliable predictor of similar events (TS Ofel), but performs poorly in short duration storms [5]. For TS Tisoy, graphical analysis of the results in comparison to the observed flood marks was conducted on two observation points. Observable floodmarks in the area, including verification with the local household affected by previous storm event (TS Tisoy) were used for evaluation. The difference ranges from about 10 to 30 cm submergence. The model has under predicted the submergence depth at the TESDA bridge by about 30 cm and about 10 cm at Purok 6 culvert road crossing.

Table 6. Computed and modelled runoff volumes for Calibrated model and during validation values including error functions.

Statistical measure	After calibration		Validation					
	TS Ambo		TS Ofel		TD Marce		TS Tisoy	
	Modeled	Observed	Modeled	Observed	Modeled	Observed	Modeled	Observed
Volume of Runoff (mm)	91.93	87.10	65.89	56.12	12.43	10.74		
Peak Discharge (cu m/sec)	6.70	6.90	3.30	3.00	1.10	0.90	9.40	
Date of Peak Discharge	15 -May - 2020	15 -May - 2020	14-Oct- 2020	14-Oct- 2020	22-Sep- 2020	22-Sep-2020	02-Dec- 2019	
Time of Peak Discharge	9:00 AM	10:00 AM	20:00	20:00	16:00	17:00	9:00	
RMSError (cu m/sec)	0.40		0.30		0.20			
Percentage Error in Volume	5.54		17.41		17.73			
Nash Sutcliffe Efficiency	0.93		0.73		-0.18			
Percentage Error in Peak (%)	2.89		10.00		22.22			
Residual	4.83		3.63		0.78			

3.2 Modeling of the downstream channel using HEC-RAS (Hydraulic analysis)

Flow conditions (Table 7) modelled in HEC HMS were used in river routing. This was included as the upstream boundary conditions that will be used in HEC RAS to model the hydraulic response of the flood plain.

Table 7. Flow conditions during model simulation using HEC RAS

Junction/ subbasin code	Description	Peak discharge
		cu. m./sec
J113	Outlet for W820	5.7
J110	Junction for W820, W830, and W930 outlets	6.5
Cubao Outlet	Watershed outlet	6.9
W830	Subbasin outlet	2.1

Critical road crossings were modeled within HEC-RAS using cutlines and measurement of culvert and bridge parameters. Hydraulic analysis yield a flood profile for all the reaches covered in the study (Figure 5). It could be observed that stations 1559.028 of the upper reach and station 1128.271 of the lower reach have the widest inundation. Flood water flowed over stream banks on sharp stream curves and flowed toward lower areas submerging part of agricultural areas in the lower reach particularly on STA's 1121.523, 559.1132, and 87.4126.

Figure 5. Water surface profile of the stream reaches using TS Ambo data

Road crossings on four (4) sections of the creek (Fig 9- a, b, c, and d) which are considered critical for human mobility were emphasized and the level of flood from the lowest points were modeled. During peak flood flow, the road crossing in Purok 6 of Barangay Mayon (Sta. 1363.815) is not passable. The depth from the lowest part of the road surface was 1.1 meters (approximate). It spans about 62 meters from end to end.

At Station 828 (Figure 6, b), water level was still within safe conditions. Depth during peak flow was at 2.51 m from the stream bed that is about 0.23 meters before reaching culvert capacity (culvert deck). This is the same for the other two stations in which the road surface is still above flood water surface levels. At Station 0 (Cubao culvert), it showed that flood water surface was about 0.45 meter before reaching the road surface level.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 6. Water surface profile on road crossing at (a) Station 136.815, Purok 6; (b) Station 828, TESDA, (c) SSC Creek road crossing; and Station 0, Sitio Cubao culvert during TS Ambo (May 14 to 15, 2020)

On the surrounding areas at station 0, it was already submerged with flood water. The depth of flood was at 0.5 m (approx.) above the surface, which is at medium severity classification. SSC road crossing (Figure 1c) is still on safe levels, although culvert capacity is full. Actual observations in the area during the storm event shows that excess storm water had accumulated on the upstream part.

4. Discussion

Evaluation of the preliminary model was done using “Goodness of fit indicators”. Objective functions for NSE, including graphical analysis of the time of peak flow indicated good relationship between the model and the observed hydrograph, except for the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) which showed less than satisfactory model performance. But in flood modelling and disaster mitigation, it is important to consider the time of peak and the peak flow as these are the factors that affect disaster prevention and mitigation [14].

Sensitivity analysis of the input parameters indicated that the Curve Number (CN) values has the highest effect on the performance of the model. The same observation was made on similar studies [15] which means that changes in these values will have a greater effect on model performance.

During calibration and optimization, adjusted parameters as a result of iteration resulted to a better model performance using another storm event. Peak discharge, peak volume and the time of peak discharge for both modeled and observed events are almost similar.

Validation of the optimized model using another storm event (TS Ofel, October 14-15, 2020) with almost the same duration resulted to a satisfactory model performance. This indicates that the model is a reliable predictor of similar events. Although some authors and the software developers had warned against model use for storm events that greatly varies with the storm event used in calibration, the model was tested using a lesser intensity and shorter duration storm (TD Marce, Sept. 22 to 23, 2020). Modeled hydrograph are almost identical with the observed event, but the time of peak flow occurrence is earlier by almost 1 hour for the model. This finding indicates the limitation of the model which is also stressed by the developers [6].

Using HEC-RAS, modeling of the stream channels especially the downstream had satisfactorily simulated a past flood event (TS Tisoy) in terms of depth on critical areas. Model output on inundated areas, including depth was also compared with observed data (TS Ofel). “Goodness-of-fit indicators”, including actual flood observations indicated that the model is a good predictor of storm events.

Right after the conduct of the study, massive infrastructure projects had been undertaken in the micro watershed including the flood basin. These include new road openings and concreting, new irrigation project, and additional flood control structures. These should be considered on future studies.

5. Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were made:

1. Models generated with GIS Aided tools and modelling applications could provide more accurate at near real-time results.
2. The calibrated model provide better results for storms of long duration such as for tropical storms as compared to low intensity, short duration storm occurrences.
3. A 7hr to 7.23 hr – 2yr storm will submerged Purok 6 road crossing and TESDA bridge with a depth of 0.5 meters.
4. Flood prevention and mitigation projects is critical at Station 136.815 (Purok 6) and Station 0 (Cubao area).

6. Patents

There are no patents resulting from the work reported in this manuscript.

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Appendix A

Figure A 1. The study area (a micro watershed at Castilla, Sorsogon)

Figure A 2. A raw Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of Mayon Micro watershed with a hillshade effect of 1

Figure A 3. land use map of the study area digitized using Arc Map and Google satellite images

Figure A 4. Flood inundation for a 10-yr flood along Mayon Creek.

Appendix B

Table A 1. Estimated Manning's n for Mayon creek channel reaches

Reach	A	B	C	D	E	Degree of meandering				Reach n
						s	m	ratio (m/s)	n value	
390	0.02	0.02	0.005	0.04	0.025	486.32	559.55	1.15	0.00	0.11
420	0.02	0.02	0.005	0.04	0.025	320.66	602.77	1.88	0.30	0.41
430	0.02	0.02	0.005	0.04	0.025	81.05	90.527	1.12	0.00	0.11
450	0.02	0.02	0.005	0.04	0.025	227.84	320.36	1.41	0.10	0.21
470	0.02	0.02	0.005	0.04	0.025	116.11	190.98	1.64	0.30	0.41
480	0.02	0.02	0.005	0.04	0.025	240.42	293.42	1.22	0.15	0.26
500	0.02	0.02	0.005	0.04	0.025	218.02	448.23	2.06	0.35	0.46

Note: (A) Basic n ; (B) Character of Channel; (C) Variation in Size and Shape; (D) Relative Effect of Obstruction; (E) Vegetation and Flow conditions; (s) straight length; (m) meandering length).

Table A 2. Precipitation data for one of the storm events used (TS Ambo, May 14 to 15, 2020) using Digitech™ Professional Wireless rain gauge, model XC040, installed at Mayon, Castilla, Sorsogon. Highlighted is the maximum 8-hr rainfall. Total = 264.2 mm.

Date	Time	Precipitation depth
		mm
May 14, 2020	11:00:00 AM	20.2
	12:00:00 PM	0.0
	1:00:00 PM	0.0
	2:00:00 PM	26.0
	3:00:00 PM	0.0
	4:00:00 PM	0.0
	5:00:00 PM	0.0
	6:00:00 PM	4.5
	7:00:00 PM	2.7
	8:00:00 PM	12.7
	9:00:00 PM	3.0
	10:00:00 PM	4.2
	11:00:00 PM	13.7
May 15, 2020	12:00:00 AM	17.0
	1:00:00 AM	15.0
	2:00:00 AM	24.5
	3:00:00 AM	31.7
	4:00:00 AM	36.0
	5:00:00 AM	25.7
	6:00:00 AM	16.0
	7:00:00 AM	4.7
	8:00:00 AM	1.2
	9:00:00 AM	2.2
	10:00:00 AM	2.0
	11:00:00 AM	0.5
	12:00:00 PM	0.0
	1:00:00 PM	0.7

References

1. Cordero, T. GMA News Online. Retrieved from GMA News: <http://www.gmanetwork.com/news/money/economy/657532/typhoons-and-flashfloods-cost-the-philippines-p6-446b-in-2017/story/> Accessed on 20 June, 2018
2. Begam, S., Ghosh, S., Jana, S., & Roy, D. Calibration and Validation of HEC HMS model for a river basin in Eastern India. *ARPN JEAS*, 2013. pp. 40-56.
3. Bhunya, P. K.. Synthetic Unit Hydrograph Methods: A Critical Review. *TOHJ*, 2011, pp 1- 8.
4. *Technical Standards and Guidelines for Planning of Flood Control Structures*. DPWH and JICA, Manila, Philippines, 2010

5. Bartles, M., Brauer, T., Ho, D., Fleming, M., Karlovits, G., Pak, J., Van, N., & Willis, J. (2016). *Hydrologic Modeling System HEC HMS User's Manual*. Davis, California, 2016,
6. Feldman, A. *HEC-HMS Technical reference Manual*. USACE, Institute for Water Resources, Hydrologic Engineering Center, California, 2000, USA.
7. Orale, R. L. Flood risk assessment in Post Antiao river control project in Catbalogan city, Philippines. *CDRJ*, 2015.. Volume 3 Issue 2. Pp 41 – 54.
8. a-a-r-s.org. Available online: <https://a-a-r-s.org/proceeding/ACRS2016/ACRS%202016%20Oral%20Papers/TS15/Ab%200116.pdf> (accessed on July 20, 2016)
9. Tiwari, B. Application of SCS-CN Method for Estimation of Runoff in a Humid Micro watershed. *IJCAS*, 2016, 74-80.
10. Napay, M. A. O; Luyun, R. A. Jr. Hydrologic modeling and flood mapping at Quinali A watershed, Albay Philippines using HEC-HMS and HEC-RAS. University of the Philipines-Los banos, laguna Philippines. 2018.
11. Nash, J. E. River flow forecasting through conceptual Models. *JH*, 1970, 280-290.
12. Moriasi, D. N., Arnold, J., Van Liew, M. W., Bingner, R. L., Harmel, D, R., & Vieth, T. L.. Model Evaluation Guidelines for Systematic Quantification of Accuracy in Watershed Simulations. *Transactions of the ASABE (American Society of Agricultural and Biological Engineers*, 2007, pp 885-900.
13. Brunner, G., Ackerman, C., & Goodel, C. HEC RAS River Analysis System User's Manual. Davis, California: USACE Institute for Water Resources, Hydrologic Engineering Center, 2016.
14. Balete, M. A., Miguel, K., & Tassew, B. G. Application of HEC-HMS Model for Flow simulation in the lake Tana basin: The case of Gilgel Abay Catchment, Upper Blue Nile Basin, Ethiopia. *H*, 2019. pp 6-21.
15. Ashraf, A., Babar, M., Lund, J., Memon, A., & Soomro, A. Sensitivity of Direct Runoff to curve number using the SCS CN Method. *CEJ*, 2019, pp 2738-2746.